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**Initial Report on Improving Parallel I/O, Enabling
In-situ and Compression**

WP4: Extreme-Data Analytics for Plasma Simulations

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents an overview of the I/O, in-situ data analysis, and compression strategies that we intend to use in the four Plasma-PEPSC codes: BIT1, GENE, PICongPU and Vlasiator. The evaluation of I/O workloads with performance profilers, such as Darshan, has revealed potential I/O bottlenecks in some of the application, allowing us to plan for targeted I/O performance improvements. Leveraging code profiling and existing knowledge of I/O performance, we have identified areas for enhancement and outlined future development plans.

In general, the adoption of openPMD API is a key strategy for supporting parallel I/O and overlap I/O and computation in the Plasma-PEPSC codes, allowing flexibility with different established parallel I/O backends, including ADIOS-2 and HDF5. The BIT1 code will integrate the openPMD approach, following the successful PICongGPU model that already uses openPMD. The GENE team plans to improve GENE by incorporating in-situ data analysis, drawing from valuable experiences gained in the ADMIRE project.

While parallel I/O may not be the primary bottleneck in upgraded codes, the challenge lies in optimizing the overlap between memory throughput and compute intensity. To address this issues, compression methods including reduced precision and machine learning approaches will be employed. GENE's next implementation step involves scaling with mixed precision, promising insights into further performance enhancements. In addition, the exploration of application-level compression schemes will be critical in guiding future optimizations for all four codes.

Acronyms

ADIOS 2 Adaptable Input/Output System, Version 2 (<https://adios2.readthedocs.io/>)

alpaka *Abstraction Library for Parallel Kernel Acceleration* (<https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka>)

Alpine IBM Spectrum Scale parallel file system (<https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/olcf-resources/data-visualization-resources/alpine/>)

API application programming interface

BIT1 BIT1 code (<https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1/>)

BLAS Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms

CFD computational fluid dynamics

Conduit Conduit: Simplified Data Exchange for HPC Simulations (<https://llnl-conduit.readthedocs.io/>)

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture (<https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-zone>)

Darshan Darshan: HPC I/O Characterization Tool (<https://www.anl.gov/mcs/darshan-hpc-io-characterization-tool>)

Epoch Epoch code (<https://github.com/Warwick-Plasma/epoch>)

FFT Fast Fourier Transform

FP floating point

Frontier Frontier (<https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/frontier/>)

GENE GENE code (<http://genecode.org>)

GMM Gaussian Mixture Model

HDF5 Hierarchical Data Format, Version 5 (<https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>)

HPC High Performance Computing

HPE Slingshot Hewlett Packard Enterprise Slingshot Interconnect (<https://www.hp.com/us/en/compute/hpc/slingshot-interconnect.html>)

I/O Input/Output

ISAAC *In Situ Animation of Accelerated Computations* tool (<https://computationalradiationphysics.github.io/isaac/>)

Llama Low-level abstraction of memory access (<https://github.com/alpaka-group/llama>)

ML machine learning

MPCDF Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (<https://www.mpcdf.mpg.de>)

MPG Max Planck Gesellschaft (<https://www.mpg.de/>)

MPG IPP Max-Planck Institut für Plasmaphysik (<https://www.ipp.mpg.de>)

NetCDF4 Network Common Data Form, Version 4 (<https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>)

OLCF Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (<https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/>)

oneAPI oneAPI programming model (<https://www.oneapi.io>)

openPMD open standard for particle-mesh data (<https://github.com/openPMD>)

openPMD-API Application programming interface for openPMD (<https://github.com/openPMD/openPMD-api>)

ParaView ParaView tool (<http://paraview.org>)

PFS parallel file system

PICongPU PICongPU code (<https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu>)

Posix Portable Operating System Interface

RDMA Remote Direct Memory Access

ROCm ROCm™ open software platform (<https://github.com/radeonopencompute/rocm>)

stdio standard Input/Output (I/O)

SYCL SYCL cross-platform abstraction layer (https://www.khronos.org/api/index_2017/sycl)

TB terabytes

VisIt VisIt tool (<https://visit-dav.github.io/visit-website/>)

Vlasiator Vlasiator code (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator>)

VLSV VLSV file format (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlsv>)

VTK visualisation toolkit (<https://vtk.org/>)

WIP Work in Progress

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1 Introduction

Plasma simulations on an extreme scale generate terabytes (TB) of data to be analysed for scientific discoveries. I/O at such a large scale slows down the codes and lowers the overall performance. Furthermore, with exascale simulations, we reach a state where the simulations produce more data than can realistically be stored and processed in time. Thus, efficient processing of such a large amount of data requires in-situ data analysis supported by efficient streaming models. Finally, the compression of plasma data (electromagnetic fields and distribution function information), possibly in conjunction with in-situ and in-memory calculations, enables more efficient data analysis of massive plasma simulation data.

2 I/O in Applications and Optimization

Traditionally, High Performance Computing (HPC) systems provide *Portable Operating System Interface (Posix) I/O* that is very similar to file I/O using the C standard I/O (stdio) library. Some of the operations that can be performed on files using Posix systems calls are: opening a file, reading from a file, writing to a file, closing a file. Single source stream are bottleneck for I/O demanding applications and to overcome the bandwidth limitation of network file-systems many-server approach with meta-server distribution is used. Such parallel network file-systems still provide Posix I/O for compatibility although for effective use of networked file servers optimized methods and libraries are required to be used.

2.1 State of the art I/O Libraries

The current state of the art I/O libraries act as middleware between the applications and the underlying parallel file system (PFS) for portable optimized I/O. The following I/O libraries are ubiquitously used in HPC:

MPI I/O The most versatile and MPI-tuned operation for multi-node I/O without any file format specification. Support for the underlying PFS varies and is implementation specific from both the application and MPI perspective.

HDF5 Hierarchical Data Format, Version 5 (HDF5) with parallel I/O capabilities. It is widely used for arbitrary dataset storage without metadata for dataset description. When compiled with MPI library support the underlying I/O can scale and has "raw" tuning possibilities.

NetCDF Network Common Data Form, Version 4 (NetCDF4) is a simpler application programming interface (API) than HDF5, while maintaining the same performance. User access with metadata in NetCDF4 is simpler due to flat hierarchy, which favours simpler project layout that might not be suitable for larger applications.

ADIOS 2 The Adaptable Input/Output System, Version 2 (ADIOS 2) is a High-Performance Publisher/Subscriber I/O framework. An abstraction to allow for high-performance I/O to/from storage and for in-situ processing. The latter capability

is favourable for remote access processing with limited bandwidth. Different engines such as HDF5 to read/write HDF5 files is used by ADIOS 2. FORTRAN and C are missing functionality in ADIOS 2 due to extensive use of C++ 11 support.

openPMD The open standard for particle-mesh data (openPMD) [1] is a self-descriptive metadata standard with an Open Source metadata format standard developed by the openPMD community. It consists of a common core definition shared among all applications within the openPMD ecosystem and can be flexibly extended to incorporate specific community and application based extensions to the core. In terms of I/O for high performance computing openPMD provides output via parallel HDF5, NetCDF4, ADIOS 2, visualisation toolkit (VTK) and Epoch code (Epoch) SDF, enabling Catalyst usage, streaming workflows [2] and in-memory compression [3]. It is used by a variety of plasma simulation codes and has applications beyond plasma physics due to its open core description of the fundamental data structures used in plasma simulation, specifically meshes and particles. Implementation of openPMD in plasma simulation codes can be best achieved via the Application programming interface for openPMD (openPMD-API) and is considered as one of the routes towards Exascale-I/O and streaming capabilities in Plasma-PEPSC.

2.2 Current Support for I/O in Plasma-PEPSC Applications

The tremendous amount of particles and plasma distribution function information in the state of the art simulations, and orders of magnitude more in future exascale runs, poses great challenges to data storage and processing. Depending on the interest the data is sized to foreseeable post processing and available throughput. Table 1 on current I/O support of Plasma-PEPSC shows implementation details and libraries used. Dominantly,

	BIT	GENE	PIConGPU	Vlasiator
Main Application Area	Plasma–Material Interfaces	Magnetically Confined Plasmas	Plasma Accelerators, High energy density physics	Space Plasmas
Parallel I/O	MPI I/O	MPI I/O Support for HDF5 and ADIOS2	OpenPMD API (parallel HDF5, ADIOS1, ADIOS2, JSON, netCDF, ...) - Integration into PANDAS + DASK	MPI I/O via VLSV
I/O Size – Simulation Results	Checkpointing: 10-20 GB Diagnostic: 9 x #snapshots GB	Checkpointing: distribution function (10–1000 GB)	100 GB – 100 TByte per time step, ~100 TB – 10 PByte for a full run with I/O every 100 time steps	Typically, 10–20 GB of spatial data and 10–20 GB for velocity space information every 1 s of simulation. Checkpointing: Full system at ~5 TB.

Table 1: Current I/O support characteristics of the Plasma-PEPSC codes.

MPI I/O is being implemented in Plasma-PEPSC codes. BIT1 code (BIT1) actually uses Posix I/O with parallel MPI rank checkpointing that requires post-processing to combine complete results. GENE supports HDF5 and ADIOS2 checkpointing. PIconGPU can use different underlying engines within openPMD API and that eases use of external tools such as Python with PANDAS library and DASK framework for distributed postprocessing. Vlasiator developed a custom MPI I/O library with VLSV file format (VLSV) that provides high level API to I/O and eases analysis.

2.3 I/O Profiling of Plasma-PEPSC Applications

Code I/O performance characterisation is required for derivation of optimisation approaches and to automatically define PFS settings, such as file stripes on Lustre, frequency I/O, write intensity, data-prefetching, data layout, MPI I/O (data sieving, two-phase collective, data request scheduling), ADIOS2 and compression algorithms.

An initial I/O profiling has been performed on the codes with known I/O limitations targeting the specific potential bottlenecks on systems available to the developers.

2.3.1 BIT1

The I/O performance of BIT1 has been analyzed when the diagnostics have been activated. To better understand the I/O performance, a simulation with 1,000 time steps has been used.

Diagnostics output (with BIT1 I/O flags `slow=1` for plasma profiles and distribution functions, `slow1` for self-consistent atomic collision diagnostics, generating the required `.dat` files) has been obtained every 100 cycles and checkpointing files (so-called `.dmp` files) every 333 cycles.

The read operations are limited to read the simulation input files which happens only once at the beginning of the simulation. The focus has been only on analysing the performance of the write operations.

Figure 1: BIT1 I/O Write Bandwidth, measured in MiB/s

BIT1 performs Posix I/O, e.g. each MPI process writes its own diagnostics and checkpointing files. Figure 1 presents the write bandwidth results, measured with Darshan: HPC I/O Characterization Tool (Darshan) for the increasing number of MPI processes (up to 12,800 MPI processes) in the two test cases.

The two plots in Figure 1 show that the write bandwidth increases with the number of MPI processes, and then it saturates, for the both test cases. The write bandwidth saturates approximately at 300 MiB/s and 70 GiB/s for the Ionization and Sheath test cases, respectively. The peak I/O write bandwidth depends on the problem size. After the peak I/O is reached, the performance degrades as the metadata writing cost increases [4].

2.3.2 PIConGPU

For the PIConGPU code (PIConGPU), we evaluate I/O performance on the Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (OLCF) Summit compute system and give a peek into Work in Progress (WIP) efforts on OLCF Frontier. The measurements include the throughput of file I/O, as well as the (perceived) throughput of streaming I/O, measured from a second application running concurrently to PIConGPU and loading all data via the highspeed network¹ that would otherwise be written to disk. This is the *perceived* throughput since it includes communication overhead of data load requests and is hence a lower approximation for the actual throughput.

From the code logic inside PIConGPU, it does not matter if the write target is the parallel file system or another application running on the same system.

The benchmark results on Summit are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: An evaluation of PIConGPU’s I/O on the Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (OLCF) Summit compute system using ADIOS2 file (yellow line) and streaming (blue line) I/O. The green line can be ignored for the purpose of this report as its performance is skewed by the chosen strategy for node-level data aggregation. The peak write throughput of the used parallel filesystem (IBM Spectrum Scale parallel file system (Alpine)) is 2.5 TiB/s.

¹Infiniband on OLCF Summit, Hewlett Packard Enterprise Slingshot Interconnect (HPE Slingshot) on OLCF Frontier

The results for file I/O demonstrate two things: (i) That PIconGPU’s output is large enough to run into the bandwidth of the installed IBM Spectrum Scale parallel file system (Alpine) (2.5 TiB, marked as a horizontal line) at a mediocre scale already, and (ii) that the I/O system of PIconGPU is able to make use of the bandwidth provided by Summit.

The streaming throughput shows not only that streaming I/O performance is naturally independent of the file system restrictions, but that higher throughputs are achieved than what the file system can do (a total throughput of ~ 9 TiB/s at 1024 nodes).

In preparation for more complex streaming-based setups, we are currently evaluating the performance of streaming I/O on OLCF Frontier. Preliminary incomplete results are printed in Table 2. They show a solid achieved throughput of ~ 3 GiB/s per node, scaling

no. of nodes	throughp./node [GiB/s]		throughp. total [TiB/s]	
	<i>low</i>	<i>high</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>high</i>
4096	2.7	3.7	12	15
(*)4096	3.6	4.7	14	19
7168	2.7	3.3	19	23
8192	2.7	3.3	21	26
9126	2.6	3.3	23	29

Table 2: A first peek into current throughput benchmarks of PIconGPU for streaming I/O with openPMD and ADIOS2 on OLCF Frontier. These results give a first feasibility estimate and are not yet in any publishable state. Most important is the solid scaling up to the full system size. The line marked with an asterisk (*) indicates an alternative streaming I/O backend implementation based on libfabric (rather than on the MPI port API used so far) that has become usable only very recently and further improves the perceived throughput.

from 4096 to 9126 compute nodes (9472 nodes being the number of available compute nodes on the system). This translates to a throughput of ~ 12 to ~ 15 TiB/s at 4096 compute nodes (half scale) and of ~ 23 to ~ 29 TiB/s at 9126 compute nodes (near full scale).

An optimized implementation that uses libfabric for connection-less Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) (rather than MPI’s `MPI_Open_Port()` API for connected communication) is currently being benchmarked, but results are at the time available only at 4096 compute nodes. Those results demonstrate an expected improvement of perceived throughput, achieving between 3.6 and 4.7 GiB/s per node at 4096 nodes, which translates to a total system-wide throughput of ~ 11 to ~ 19 TiB/s.

These results, while preliminary and yet incomplete, are a practical demonstration of PIconGPU’s ability to do massive I/O at full scale of the current TOP1 HPC system using the openPMD-API.

2.3.3 Vlasiator

In order to investigate I/O performance of Vlasiator, the Darshan tool is used. Darshan is an I/O characterization tool that automatically instruments applications and provides information about I/O transfers, including MPI-I/O. At this point, first tests have been

performed on Vlasiator using a small 3-dimensional magnetosphere simulation running on 128 MPI ranks. Two test procedures have been performed. The first test performs a regular run that prints out reduced data at the start and the end, as well as a full system check at the end (1). The second test reads in the previous checkpoint, propagates for the same time as the previous run and writes out a new checkpoint (2). The according bandwidths captured with Darshan are shown in the first two blocks in Table 3. The last block shows test (1) with a larger problem size on 1280 MPI ranks, writing intermediate data as well as the final system check. We can observe a peak I/O transfer rate of 1897.97 MiB/s for the realistic problem size.

Test	File	Data Size [MiB]	I/O Operation	Bandwidth [MiB/s]
(1)	Bulk0	29.2	W	128.78
	Bulk1	30.5	W	116.71
	SystemCheck0	1655.0	W	1190.80
(2)	Bulk2	31.0	W	73.36
	SystemCheck0	1653.8	R	1453.26
	SystemCheck1	1719.6	W	1237.90
(1)	Bulk0	2359.6	W	1256.16
	Bulk1	2363.9	W	1144.11
	Bulk2	2365.6	W	1177.91
	SystemCheck0	30534.3	W	1897.97

Table 3: First Vlasiator I/O performance profiling results with Darshan. The first two blocks show consecutive tests on a small data set, where test (2) uses the checkpoint of test (1). The bottom block of rows shows test (1) performed on a larger problem.

These results provide first insights into Vlasiator’s I/O performance, and an investigation of the scalability will be conducted as a next step. The Vlasiator team has also improved the functionality of the VLSV I/O library to support more aggressive packaging of multiread calls during checkpoint restarting. Merging of this functionality is pending more detailed profiling using Darshan.

2.3.4 GENE

Neither GENE code (GENE) nor GENE-X did suffer from I/O performance problems and therefore no profiling have been done yet on these codes. Increasing the problem size on the way to the target challenge, I/O performance might get a bit more into our focus but this has not started, yet.

2.4 I/O Optimization Strategies

I/O has been and will remain a major challenge for simulation codes. Simulation codes are often memory bound, thus favoring a weak scaling approach in order to make use of all available GPU memory on large systems. For I/O, this implies that the size of a single raw data dump is bound by the sum of all available/used GPU memory. The

feasibility of classical file I/O is coming to an end along with these estimations due to lacking parallel file system bandwidths and capacities.

Accordingly, file I/O needs to be optimized for scalable simulation runs within the boundaries of what is still possible, while at the same time alternative approaches need to be explored beyond those boundaries. One such approach that has been pioneered by PIconGPU is streaming I/O, where I/O is no longer written to the file system, but rather transported via the system’s network to an analysis code running concurrently. From a high-level view, this analysis performs a domain-specific data reduction.

Figure 3: Software stack for I/O with the openPMD-API, currently used in PIconGPU (and other non-PEPSC codes). The I/O library backends along with their data transports and storages can be chosen and configured as command-line parameters without recompilation.

An important key in the pursuit of these performance goals – file I/O and beyond-file I/O alike – is performance portability. The I/O system of PIconGPU has hence outsourced most of its low-level system-specific I/O optimizations to an external library openPMD-API, which implements an established data standard of the laser-plasma simulation community (openPMD). The resulting software stack is seen in Figure 3.

This approach enables a rapid adoption of I/O solutions and optimizations for new setups as well as accessibility to performance features of openPMD-API and its backends ADIOS2 and HDF5 (e.g. node-level data aggregation, file system specific settings such as OST usage or striping, low-level transport) for optimizing file I/O setups, while enabling an non-intrusive transition to streaming I/O. The backend for streaming I/O is ADIOS2 with whose developers there exists a well-established collaboration.

3 In-situ Data Analysis

At Exascale, large scale I/O (> 10 PByte) is limited by the lifetime on the hard drive and by the size and throughput of the high-throughput hard drive partition for analysis. Therefore, in-situ data analysis will become much more common. In-situ visualization with a graphics pipeline and post-processing data analysis with pipelined filters

can provide valuable insights by storing the temporal evolution of the simulation for interactive preview and instant review. This co-processing of data while the simulation is running does not slow down the simulation and can be detached/attached at any time with tools such as ParaView, VisIt, *In Situ Animation of Accelerated Computations* tool (ISAAC) and other custom visualisation tools. The benefits of in-situ analysis are flexibility, easier selection and thus reduction of total data for analysis. Plasma-PEPSC provides one of the main developers (HZDR) of the open standard for particle-mesh data openPMD ecosystem. openPMD is a schema and standardisation effort to be adopted by the Plasma-PEPSC applications. The adoption of in-situ by the codes is accompanied with adaptation of in-memory mesh-representation from code point-of-view to on-the-fly viewable-ready or at least graphics-pipeline ready representation. Such in-core data coupling, serialization, and I/O tasks for describing hierarchical scientific data can be accomplished by the Conduit: Simplified Data Exchange for HPC Simulations (Conduit) library that follows "Mesh Blueprint" for a common way to describe computational simulation meshes.

3.1 Current Support for in-situ Data Analysis in Plasma-PEPSC Applications

Current in-situ support is implemented in PIconGPU only, with a custom developed tool ISAAC that is an in-situ rendering library [5] using a tight coupling approach that enables direct integration into any particle-mesh based simulation software. ISAAC is implemented via the *Abstraction Library for Parallel Kernel Acceleration* (alpaka) [6, 7] and utilizes ICE-T [8] for scaling across nodes and inter-node composition of the visualization stream. It was directly coupled to the particle-in-cell code PIconGPU allowing a visualization of plasma simulations while they are running on a compute cluster. With interactive steering, selection of various data sources and various options to visualize, scientists can get a first view into their simulation enabling early insights into relevant physics and thus a faster return in developing problem-specific data analysis workflows (e.g. using ADIOS2, openPMD). Due to the tight coupling, ISAAC directly accesses PIconGPU data. While this tightly coupled in-situ approach allows for the fastest data access, the flexible design of ISAAC ensures the option to implement this library into other simulation software as well. In order to ensure scalability of the PIconGPU and ISAAC in situ workflow on the newest AMD hardware, as used by e.g. EuroHPC's LUMI system, we performed a scaling test using the recently added vector field visualization method. We performed these scaling tests on Crusher, a Frontier testbed, with very similar design to LUMI prior to the availability of LUMI. The results of these scaling test have been published in [9]. To summarize, an efficient in-situ rendering of PIconGPU data was demonstrated up to a rate of 16 PiB/min, unfeasible by any storage-based post-processing approach.

Another option for enabling in-situ data analysis is using the ADIOS 2 [10, 11], originally designed as an high-level Input/Output (IO) framework. Its independence from the VTK data format and compatibility with diverse data formats makes it an ideal choice for in-situ frameworks. With ADIOS 2 offering high-level APIs for C/C++, and Python, it simplifies the development of adaptor functions and also provides possibilities to run asynchronous in-situ task. Within the framework of the ADMIRE EuroHPC project, we

have successfully used ADIOS to develop a framework for in-situ processing, allowing different execution models (synchronous, asynchronous, and hybrid), depending on the characteristics of the simulation and in-situ tasks. Within ADMIRE, this framework has been successfully tested with different in-situ tasks in a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) (NEK5000) and molecular dynamics (QuantumEspresso) application [12, 13]. As openPMD has inherent ADIOS 2 support these findings can be directly transferred to openPMD.

3.2 Potential In-situ Data Analysis in Plasma-PEPSC Application

For BIT1, there is great potential for in-situ data analysis and visualization with openPMD and the ADIOS2 backend. Steps have already been made in this direction by creating a branch `feature/cplusplus`, converting the `main()` function from C language to C++ language in order to accommodate the openPMD library and the *parallel write* example in openPMD repository (https://github.com/openPMD/openPMD-api/blob/dev/examples/5_write_parallel.cpp) has been successfully reproduced with BIT1.

Building on the ADMIRE developments discussed above, we plan to use ADIOS as in-situ framework for GENE-X and started to explore how to use it for data compression and visualization in-situ tasks. Here, synergies with the openPMD developments around ADIOS 2 will be leveraged.

Building upon openPMD and the underlying protocol (Catalyst, ADIOS2) Vlasiator will benefit with the in-situ approach.

Another benefit of Catalyst is that can be used as I/O layer to ADIOS2 which practically removes requirement for own storage I/O using single in-situ library for visualisation and storage. Yet, such approach will need to be tested.

4 Compression Methods

The four flagship codes enable simulations requiring a large amount of data to be handled during simulations, such as intra- and inter-node communication and in I/O tasks such as checkpointing. The communication leads to increased energy consumption and performance overhead. Compression methods are vital to combat the scaling limits for high-performance plasma simulations.

4.1 State of the Art Compression Libraries

Scientific Compression Libraries for Plasma Simulation Codes The use of data compression has been a recurring topic in HPC as a way to address the existing gap between computing and storage/interconnect capabilities of modern supercomputers. Historically, two forms of compressors have been explored: *lossless* and *lossy*. The former group of compressors enables users to recover the exact data while reducing data size. Thanks to this one-to-one mapping between original and compressed data, scientists and applications developers do not concern themselves with introducing errors to numerical simulations. However, even floating-point oriented lossless compressors (FPZIP[14],

ndzip-gpu[15], FPC [16]) are well known to achieve only small reductions in data size, due to existing randomness of mantissa-bits in scientific data [17]. Compression is inherently affected by the computational time spent on compression, giving rise to limits on throughput enhancements due to compression as observed in real life applications such as PIconGPU [3].

It is precisely the requirement of having no information loss that limits the achievable compression ratios of lossless compressors [18]. *Lossy* compressors, on the other hand, build on the fact that numerical simulations inherently involve round-off and truncation of floating point values as well as model errors, hinting that approximate compressed data would still provide acceptable simulation outputs. Lossy methods then provide improved compression ratios at the cost of some information loss [14]. During the past decade, the HPC community has seen significant progress in the development of error-bounded lossy compressors for scientific data, i.e. compressors capable of limiting data loss within an error bound [19]. Currently, error-bounded lossy compressors can be grouped into three categories [20, 21]: prediction-based compressors like the SZ family of compressors [22, 23, 24, 25], transform-based compressors, such as ZFP [26, 27] and the more recently proposed multilevel data reduction methods like MGARD [28, 29, 30]. SZ and ZFP are currently regarded as the best lossy compressors with error control in terms of compression quality and execution throughput [31, 32]. Parallelized, in-situ implementations of such compressors are key to maximize throughput for applications [3].

Despite the advances in lossy compression for scientific data, there is still no certain guide on its use and impact in applications. In particular, the choice of a compressor for a particular use case, expected data compressibility and impact of compression on quantities of interest resulting of a simulation are some of the open questions in the field [31].

4.1.1 Machine Learning Approaches

In recent years, the work on machine learning (ML) approaches for data-intensive tasks such as image recognition and language modeling led to unprecedented scientific successes. ML is closely related to data representation and function approximation and is a natural topic to explore for finding algorithms to improve compression. A common ML technique for compression is to use autoencoders, which is a type of neural network that has been taught to encode data into a compressed format such as a lower dimensional representation, a corresponding decoder is then used to recover the original data. Autoencoders has been used on scientific data in [33], variations of autoencoders include variational autoencoders, which introduce probabilistic elements, making the latent space more structured [34]. Many Neural network architectures, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) or recurrent neural networks (RNNs), can be trained to compress data directly. These networks can learn complex patterns and representations that are more efficient than traditional compression algorithms for specific types of data, such as physical fields [35, 36]. Neural networks can be used together with conventional methods to improve the performance. Some techniques that can be improved are entropy coding schemes like Huffman coding or arithmetic coding, improving the efficiency of these traditional compression techniques [37].

Methods not based on neural networks: Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) can describe

the correlation of the pixel information in the case that GMM can fit any probability density function well with enough number of distributions. This can be used to compress data in codes that represent physical fields [38]. Dictionary learning algorithms, such as sparse coding, can be used to find an over-complete basis set that represents the data with sparsity. This learned dictionary can then be used for compression by representing data using a combination of sparse dictionary elements [39].

An important question is how ML methods should be used to efficiently leverage their properties: traditional ML develops a model for isolated tasks, and this can lead to a prohibitively high training cost. Transfer learning introduces a more Bayesian perspective where new tasks rely on previous knowledge.

4.2 Reduced-Precision Methods

There are two floating point (FP) types available across all common programming languages and hardware platforms: 32-bit IEEE `single` precision (numbers range from roughly 10^{-38} to 10^{+38} , relative accuracy of about 7 significant decimal digits) and 64-bit IEEE `double` precision (range from roughly 10^{-308} to 10^{+308} , relative accuracy of about 16 significant decimal digits). For numerical studies scientists usually default to run their simulations in `double` precision. This is often sufficient to avoid dealing with finite precision induced instabilities. Running the application in `single` precision instead, due to the 50% reduced memory consumption, can yield a 2x speedup. To benefit from this potential performance gain, however, the underlying algorithmic parts and the resulting output — often statistical quantities of interest — have to be sufficiently robust with respect to the reduced accuracy of `single` precision.

As the impressive compute power of (pre-) Exascale systems is mainly provided by GPUs, even smaller size FP types are available: 16-bit IEEE `half` precision (ignoring subnormals numbers range from $1/16384$ to 65504 , with a relative accuracy of about 3 significant decimal digits) and 16-bit non-IEEE `bfloat16` (range like `single`, relative accuracy of about 2 to 3 significant decimal digits), as well as 8-bit FP types (not considered further here). The 16-bit types can lead to a 4x speedup compared to `double` precision for memory-bound kernels. Due to the over-provisioning of certain low-precision operations via tensor cores even performance gains of up to a full order of magnitude are achievable for eligible compute-bound kernels as demonstrated in the HPL-MxP benchmark [40].

An immediate obstacle using these 16-bit FP types is the far-from-mature language and software support. While GPU vendors provide corresponding 16-bit types as part of their C++ APIs (i.e., Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA), ROCm™ open software platform (ROCm), or SYCL cross-platform abstraction layer (SYCL) via Intel oneAPI programming model (oneAPI)), there is no corresponding Fortran type and only the upcoming C++23 standard is expected to provide the 16-bit types as part of the standard library. As a natural consequence common libraries (e.g., for Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) or Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms (BLAS)) often are only applicable to `single` or `double` precision data.

Apart from these technical obstacles the crucial restriction is the drastically reduced relative accuracy of the 16-bit FP types (and for `half` precision also the small range), which limits their (straightforward) usage for various algorithms. Some of an application's subroutines might be robust enough to produce outputs of acceptable accuracy, while

other routines could be too sensitive to directly allow for any precision lower than `single` (or even `double`). Hence, a feasible approach could be to run only selected parts of an application in lower precision. For more sensitive routines, or those which have to produce a high precision result, it might be possible to modify them in order to employ a mixed precision method. In certain scenarios it is possible to benefit from the faster execution of lower precision computations (e.g., `single`), while recovering a higher precision accurate result (e.g., `double`).

The prime example of such a mixed precision method is iterative refinement [41]. There, the compute-intensive LU decomposition of a linear system of equations is carried out in low accuracy. Then, the obtained low accuracy solution to the system is iteratively improved by solving for the high precision error (computationally cheap with the LU decomposition) until the high accuracy is reached.

We note that most of the literature in the field [42, 43, 44] is applying mixed precision methods to linear algebra routines, such that successful exploitation of the ideas in (parts of) the flagship codes might require novel research. Nevertheless, due to the potential performance gains it is worth investigating the possibilities to use reduced precision methods in the four flagship codes.

4.3 Potential of Compression and Reduced Precision Methods in Plasma-PEPSC

Considering the machine balance (per cycle ratio of FP versus memory operations) of modern hardware, in order to maximize performance the four flagship codes must strive to maximize data locality as well as compute intensity per accessed FP value. Further, to reduce (MPI-) communication overhead they must minimize data transfer amounts across compute nodes and through memory hierarchies. Hence, a quantitative reduction of the particle and field data (in Bytes, per value as well as in total) would directly impact the runtime of a simulation.

Physical constraints usually restrict space and time resolution, hence the amount of data points in a simulation can not be reduced below a certain threshold. Keeping the physically prescribed resolution data amounts can still be reduced by floating point data compression (see Section 4.1 above) or by choosing smaller size floating point formats (see Section 4.2 above). With either approach one seeks to reduce the data amount as much as possible (higher performance, less disk storage), while still running simulations as accurately as necessary (to obtain results of acceptable accuracy).

To efficiently leverage compression and reduced precision methods in the Plasma-PEPSC codes, we must look for the specific needs and synergies between the codes. The initial work to unravel the opportunities is to perform profiling on memory, communication, and I/O. It is clear that PICongPU have identified I/O to be a main bottleneck for large-scale simulations. Meanwhile, Vlasiator is working on algorithmic changes to enable acceleration through compression and reduced precision. Reduced and mixed precision methods for storing and performing computations on fields is evaluated in BIT1 and GENE.

4.3.1 BIT1

Simulation particle information is stored in memory according to the spatial grid cell. As a result, the particles neighboring in space are also neighbors in the memory and are sorted according to the spatial cells. In this case, the maximum distance associated with the particle corresponds to the cell size and particle positions are saved as single precision float variables. In addition, it reduced the required memory and more particle and field data was stored in cache memory, increasing the probability of a “cache-hit” and the simulation speed. It also reduced the required disk space when writing the given state of large-size systems to disk. On the other hand, this approach requires an additional CPU time: each time steps some particles cross the boundary between neighboring cells and have to be rearranged in memory [45].

4.3.2 PIconGPU

The theoretical groundwork of I/O compression in PIconGPU is discussed in [46]. It observes the opposing effects of (1) reduced I/O efficiency due to computational overhead of compression and (2) improved I/O efficiency due to reduced amounts of data. The throughput gain by compression can hence be positive and negative (and both results are realistic).

In consequence, compression must be part of the I/O performance portability system in order to pick a compression that fits the current setup’s requirements. Compression is generally a runtime preference in PIconGPU and implemented via the openPMD-API and its backends (refer to Figure 3 for PIconGPU’s I/O software stack). The openPMD-API currently leverages the compression methods implemented in ADIOS2 (e.g. Blosc2, BZip2, Zfp, Mgard, Sz) and has been an important test bed for verifying their applicability and scalability. The openPMD-API does currently not leverage HDF5 compression, but it could be added without requiring code changes in PIconGPU.

PIconGPU can fully execute as a GPU-accelerated code via alpaka, with compression being “offloaded” to the CPU. CPU-based compression – while generally less efficient than on the GPU – is preferred as a way to make use of idle compute resources in a heterogeneous node that harbours both GPUs and CPUs. In this configuration the PIconGPU simulation fully stays on the GPU while compression of the code output data is performed on the CPU.

On the (non-I/O) compute side, PIconGPU is a prime example of a fully mixed-precision code. With alpaka as the underlying parallelization library portable reduced precision data types exist and are mapped to platform-dependant implementations of said data types. With physics-based tests and error propagation we check the influence of reduced precision on the physics output of the code. Already in 2013 PIconGPU could report mixed-precision floating point results in its Gordon Bell prize finalist paper [47] and the influence of mixed precision operation of the code on the physics results is well understood and controlled in the CI/CD chain.

With the recent implementation of reduced representations of C++ data types in the Low-level abstraction of memory access (Llama) library [48], Llama now provides an integrated approach of flexible, optimizable memory layout selection for user-side data types in combination with reduced precision or compressed data representation in memory. A Llama mapping between a user-side data type and its memory layout provides

the information necessary to retrieve the data values for the user-side data type from the data in memory. This mechanism is implemented for both compile time and run time and is flexible enough to integrate advanced reduction or compression algorithms including machine learning approaches. For details on the Llama library and its scope we refer to D5.1.

4.3.3 Vlasiator

Both lossy and lossless compression of the Vlasiator code (Vlasiator) velocity space data have been preliminarily studied as part of a bachelor’s thesis in 2020, but the results were not very encouraging. Due to the large dynamic range of phase space density values, the resulting floating point quantities have neither proven to be easily compressible using run-of-the-mill lossless data compression formats, nor have lossy compression methods proven to give good quality / speed tradeoffs.

One approach that has shown promise is the storage of the phase space density $f(\vec{x}, \vec{v}, t)$ in its logarithmic form, $\log(f(\vec{x}, \vec{v}, t))$. This transformation conditions the resulting floating point values to be much more amenable to compression methods, and might even enable the use of a fixed-point data representation. Alas, in a simple implementation, the back-and-forth transformation of f between the logarithmic and linear domains (as required by Vlasiator’s solvers) has proven to be a major performance bottleneck, that had prevented any production use of this implementation.

There is a hope, however, that the whole Vlasov solver could be operated in logarithmic space. As the Vlasov equation, solved by $f(\vec{x}, \vec{v}, t)$, is also solved by any differentiable function composition $g(f(\vec{x}, \vec{v}, t))$, no major code changes to the solvers themselves would be required. Data reduction method, numerical experiment code and limiters for conserved quantities however will require updating.

4.3.4 GENE

Currently, Max Planck Gesellschaft (MPG), through Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF) and Max-Planck Institut für Plasmaphysik (MPG IPP), is involved in a German-funded project titled *Data Reduction for Exascale Application in Fusion Research* (DaREXA-F). In this context, MPCDF has been exploring lossy compression methods with a focus on inter-node communication as part of distributed computations, as well as memory footprint reduction. So far, an exploration of compressors, their execution backends and capabilities has been carried out as Figure 4 shows. This experience enables us to now apply some of the lessons learned on the actual target application, GENE.

In the context of Plasma-PEPSC we will be carrying over and choosing promising compression techniques focusing in particular on improving I/O capabilities for GENE and GENE-X.

Further, also in the context of DaREXA-F, IPP has taken first steps to enable mixed precision in GENE. The GTENSOR productivity and portability library [49], which enables GENE to run on GPUs, has successfully been extended to allow for the 16-bit floating point types `half` and `bfloat16`.

Current effort is on infrastructure work within GENE itself. While GENE allows a simulation to be run completely in either `single` or `double` precision, we aim to have

Figure 4: Preliminary evaluation of error-bounded lossy compressors on a synthetic 3D smooth dataset. The figures show a comparison of ZFP and MGARD achievable compression ratios and compression/decompression throughputs when using different tolerances (MGARD) and compression rates (ZFP) on an artificial 3D dataset. Both compressors were executed using their GPU backends (MGARD-X CUDA backend and ZFP CUDA)

more fine-grained control in order to instruct selected parts of the time step (e.g., stencil computation, moments calculation, linear solver, FFT) to be run in different floating point precisions. This will give the means to establish an experimental understanding of the effect of reduced precision on different parts of GENE, which in turn will serve as a starting point to employ mixed precision strategies.

5 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we provided an initial report on the I/O, in-situ data analysis, and compression strategies of the four plasma codes. We evaluated the I/O workloads in the four codes and identified current associated bottlenecks. The I/O performance analysis is enabled by profiling the codes. Plans for future developments in the deliverable are outlined. In particular, we plan to use openPMD to support I/O in the applications. This will allow us to use different backends. BIT1 will be the first code to follow up the PIConGPU approach with openPMD. GENE team plans to upgrade the code with in-situ data analysis following the experience gained with related project developments. Parallel I/O might not be the bottleneck in upgraded codes but rather the challenge of overlap between memory throughput and compute intensity. To tackle the minimization of local memory access, compression methods with reduced precision and ML approach will provide valuable improvements. Insight into scaling with mixed precision is expected for GENE as the next implementation step. Similarly, compression at the application level will be analyzed for scaling to guide the future optimizations of the codes.

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